

NANOREINFORCEMENTS FOR CMCs

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ABSTRACT

Toughness, K_{Ic} , is an intrinsic property of a material that may be well defined by *the capability to resist to a catastrophic propagation of a crack*. As defined, is directly proportional to $(a_c)^{1/2}$ where a_c is the critical flaw length. Monolithic ceramic materials are brittle, and a_c values are in the range of the μm while metals have a_c values in the range of the mm. Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) philosophy is to achieve, through the reinforcement, a barrier to the crack growth in the matrix. Nanoreinforcements are ideal for stopping crack-growth in ceramics, because the barriers are close enough at distances below typical a_c values of the matrix.

Nanoreinforcements, referred to in this work, are highly porous material of $(\text{Si})_x(\text{O})_y(\text{C})_z$ with usually poor mechanical properties.

A stronger reinforcing network is highly desirable. In this work a carbon layer is the reinforcing agent which is obtained by phenolic or furanic polymerisation within the 3D nanostructure.

Furanic and phenolic resins are the precursor materials for the reinforcement process in this work. Their polymerisation kinetics and impregnation parameters are studied. Chemical surface treatment of the original nanoreinforcement seem to be of crucial importance in the impregnation process.

Pyrolysis of organic resins-impregnated nanoreinforcements must provide a new and stronger Si-O-C/C reinforcement ready for further treatment with liquid silicon metal to obtain a Si-C layer and therefore a new (Si-O-C/Si-C) 3D network.

Some promising preliminary results are shown.

KEYWORDS: CMC, nanoreinforcements, phenolic resins, furanic resins, surface treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Above 1000°C few materials can keep their integrity under loading conditions. Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) are candidate materials for high temperature applications in gas turbines, heat exchangers, space vehicles and nuclear reactors^{1, 2, 3}. While significant improvements have been made in fracture toughness in several ceramics, lack of reliability and defect tolerance have proved to be major limiting factors in the future application of ceramics in high temperature structural components. Indication that these problems might be overcome by CMCs, pushed scientists in the research of these materials. The oxidation behavior of carbon fibers was a limitation but the availability of the polycarbosilane derived SiC fiber, Nicalon in the early 1980's, gave expectation of improved oxidation resistance. Nicalon/glass ceramic composites were trailed in a US military jet engine development programme in 1993. The need to increase temperature capability over that of glass ceramic matrix composites led to the incorporation of SiC matrices. The manufacturing process involved chemical vapor infiltration using a gaseous precursor such as chlorosilane, or infiltration with a carbosilane polymer precursor, and pyrolysis. Both processes are slow, and densification of the material is not easily achieved.

A key factor is the interface behavior. The properties of the fiber-matrix interface are of prime importance in determining composite behavior. With interfaces of appropriate strength, fiber debonding, fiber fracture and fiber pull-out act to improve the toughness of composites. In composite systems such as SiC/glass ceramic, a very thin (10-40 μm) carbon rich layer is formed at the fiber/matrix interface during processing. This layer is believed to form a bond strong enough for load transfer yet weak enough to debond and allow fiber pull-out. Still, oxidative instability at high temperature, results in disappearance of the layer and toughness reduction⁴. We found described⁵ a work on the extension of the nozzle of a HM7 engine for the third phase of Ariane. The materials used were NOVOTEX /SEPCARBINOX. The former, carbon-based reinforcement, is a 3D

network, easy to adapt to any shape. The latter, the SiC matrix, provided dimensional stability and oxidation resistance.

In this paper we start with a 3D nanoreinforcement obtained by pyrolysis of carbosilane polymeric gels, which are highly porous material with usually poor mechanical properties.

We pretend to reinforce this basic 3D network with carbon layer and protect the resulting reinforcement against oxidation. The methodology to cover the network surface with phenolic and furanic resins, carbon-precursors, is described. Preliminary results are given in which we can verify the major influence of the quality of the interface.

Polymerization reactions, to take place must meet some requirements of different nature, chemical, thermodynamic and of physical character.

Chemical requirements are those related to the nature of terminal groups of the potential reactants, which should be at least bifunctional.

Thermodynamic requirements are those of general character for all spontaneous process to take place, which is bound to mean a decrease in the Gibbs free energy of the system ΔG that is temperature-dependent and integrates two terms according to the expression

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T \Delta S \quad (1)$$

where ΔH is the polymerisation enthalpy and ΔS the change of entropy in the polymerisation.

The physicochemical requirements are those related with the necessary mobility of the molecules in the reaction medium and that the active groups are not sheltered by neighbouring groups or by chains that prevent migration.

A Dynamic Analyser is an instrument that allows monitoring changes in viscoelastic properties of a material put between two parallel plates and a sinusoidal strain is applied to the sample. Measurement of the generated sinusoidal strength, allows monitoring the shear modulus at any moment and therefore the viscosity variation.

We measure the *gelification time*, or time needed for a certain resin, to reach the G'/G'' crossover point at a given temperature, where G' is the storage modulus and G'' is the loss modulus in shear. to obtain a mathematical expression of this parameter, supposed to be in relation with rate of polymerisation, and the temperature. Gelification times can then be calculated at different temperatures, which provide us with the tool to adjust and optimise the nanoreinforcement impregnation process.

THEORY

VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF POLIMERIC MATERIALS

In viscoelastic studies of polymeric materials the method of sinusoidal excitation and response is very useful⁶. In this case the applied deformation and the resulting force both vary sinusoidally with time, the rate being specified by the frequency in Hz or radians/sec. For linear viscoelastic behaviour, the stress will alternate sinusoidally but will be out of phase with the applied strain. This phase lag results from the time necessary for molecular rearrangements and is associated with relaxation phenomena. The strain (action) and the stress (reaction) are expressed as follows:

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 \text{sen}(\omega t) \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \text{sen}(\omega t + \delta) = \sigma_0 \cos \delta \text{sen}(\omega t) + \sigma_0 \text{sen} \delta \cos(\omega t) \quad (3)$$

Where ω is the angular frequency and δ the phase angle. The stress can be considered to consist of two components, one in phase with the strain σ' and the other 90° out of phase σ'' .

The stress divided by the strain gives the modulus:

$$G = \sigma(t) / \gamma(t) \quad (4)$$

We can split the modulus into an in-phase, G' (real) and an out-of-phase, G'' (imaginary) component. The real part of the modulus G' is called the storage modulus because it is related to the storage of energy as

potential energy and its release in the periodic deformation. The imaginary part of the modulus is associated with the dissipation of energy as heat when materials are deformed:

$$G' = \sigma' / \gamma \quad \text{and} \quad G'' = \sigma'' / \gamma \quad (5)$$

The loss tangent, $\tan \delta$, is called internal friction or damping, and is the ratio of the loss modulus to the storage modulus.

$$\tan \delta = G'' / G' \quad (6)$$

Monomers become polymers in various phases, which schematically can be divided according to some authors⁷ in the step-reaction and chain-reaction polymerisation. The first step takes place between two polyfunctional molecules to produce a large polyfunctional molecule and is the step in which chains grow. The second takes place between branched chains and produces cross-linking and a network structure with an outstanding increase in the viscosity (gelation).

The viscoelastic character of polymers is much related to their molecular structure and changes in these properties are observed during the polymerisation progress. Measurement of viscoelastic properties (G' and G'') along time at any temperature allows monitoring the gelification of a resin.

Much research can be found in the literature using this technique for a great number of applications like molecular weight determination, curing curves studies, etc.^{8 9 10 11 12}.

RATE OF CURING OF A RESIN:

When a layer of resin is cured between the plates of the Dynamic Analyser, at a controlled temperature, there is a parameter which is very sensitive to the rate of the gelification process and that is the *gelification time* t_g , or the time needed to reach the crossover point of the curves of G' and G'' versus time. This magnitude increases inversely with temperature of the plates and a connection can be drawn with the rate of curing at each temperature. A mathematical expression of this parameter with temperature of curing is attained in this work.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Resins:

Several phenolic resins (Resol Type) and several furanic resins from Bakelite Ib., S.A. are used.

Reinforcements:

Four reinforcements, made by pyrolysis of carbosilane derivatives are used, prepared by the Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio, CSIC.

Instruments:

The Dynamic Analyser is a RDA II of Rheometrics. The Transducer and the phase angle are calibrated before testing using calibrated weights and steel rectangular sample, respectively according with the instrument specifications. Testing conditions are:

Geometry: Parallel Plates.

Plates Diameter: 25/25 mm.

Gap: 0.1-0.3 mm

Frequency: 10 rad seg^{-1} .

Initial strain: 50 %. Autostrain option to keep stress in range.

Temperature: Ramps to obtain gelification temperatures, T_{gel} , and different temperatures below T_{gel} to obtain mathematical relations.

Apparent density is measured in a GeoPyc 1360 equipment of Micromeritics.

Bulk density is measured in a Accupyc 1330 equipment of Micromeritics.

Optical microscopy images are obtained in a Leitz MM6 instrument

SEM images are obtained in a Jeol JSM840 instrument.

Mechanical tests have been performed in an Instron 4502

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

REINFORCEMENTS

In figs 1 to 4 we can observe SEM images (1x500) of the four reinforcements as received.

Fig. 1 Reinforcement 1 (1x500)

Fig.2. Reinforcement 2 (1x500)

Fig 3. Reinforcement 3. (1x500)

Fig. 4. Reinforcement 4 (1x500)

From them we can roughly estimate that the porous cut-sections are bigger in R1 and R3 (20 to 50 μm), and smaller in R2 and R4 (1 to 10 μm).

Once cleared the channels of detached particles, the measured bulk and apparent densities, the %weight of C and % vol porosity are those shown in table I.

Table 1. Properties of nanoreinforcements

Reinforcement	Carbon content % w	Apparent density g/cc	Bulk density g/cc	Porosity %v
R1	8	0.60	2.08	71
R2	8	0.60	2.10	72
R3	10	0.61	2.11	71
R4	10	0.61	2.08	71

PARAMETERS AFFECTING THE IMPREGNATION PROCESS.

The chosen polymers are blends, with small size active monomers, to obtain very fluid resins in order to be able to fill the smaller voids of the nanoreinforcements. According to the literature the higher carbon yields, after pyrolysis, is obtained with phenolic and furanic resins¹³, in the order of 50-60% weight.

Polymerisation should occur primarily on the wall-surface of the reinforcements and mildly enough to avoid gas entrapping and fast enough as to complete filling of channels and liberation of reaction gases before the viscosity of the bulk polymer is too high. The viscosity of the blends is greatly affected by the temperature, and also the gelification time t_g , which is a limiting value of reaction time.

We must find a compromise **temperature/time of reaction** to optimise the filling of the nanoreinforcements.

The other important parameter is the surface free energy of the channel walls. That is why we have tried some surface treatments before impregnation.

The amount of reinforcement available was very small, so only a limited number of tests could be performed.

TEMPERATURE/TIME OF REACTION OF RESINS.KINETICS

A first comparative estimation of the values of temperatures of gelification of the different blends can be obtained with a standard temperature ramp run in the Dynamic Analyser. From these experiments we can estimate *gelification temperatures* (limiting parameter) shown in table 2.

Table 2. Curing ramp of five resin blends

Resin blend	Tgel (°C)	Time gel (min)	min viscosity (P)
Fe1	127	35	0.3-0.5
Fe2	136	39	0.3-0.5
Feb	133	38	0.3-0.5
Fux	142	42	0.3-0.5
Fuy	155	49	0.3-0.5

For each of these blends a kinetic study is made by measuring the gelification time, t_g , isothermally at different temperatures below those in table 2. We consider the gel point the crossover point of G' and G'' . The experimental values are shown in fig 5 for phenolic and furanic blends Fe2 and Fux.

Fig.5. Experimental t_g values versus temperature in phenolic and furanic blends.

Gel times fit fairly well to an exponential curve, once tg^0 is calculated by multiple approximation system.

The parameter we consider directly proportional to the rate of curing is $1/(tg-tg^0)$, according to a previous work¹⁴, and fits well to an Arrhenius formulation:

$$v = v_0 \exp(-\Delta H/RT) \quad (7)$$

where v is in this case the inverse of the gel time and ΔH the enthalpy of the reaction that can be calculated from the above measurements.

Values found for Fe2 and Fux blends are 43 kcal/mol and 37 kcal/mol respectively.

We show the values of these two blends because both are the ones we have found most successful in the *trial and error* method for optimisation of infiltration conditions.

Surface Treatments

All surfaces were dehydrated before infiltration, which is made in controlled atmosphere. This process is named here treatment T.

Furanic blends are sensitive to the chemical modification of the surface before infiltration. These reactions are named as treatments A, B, C.

Impregnation conditions

Several impregnation conditions, temperature/time profiles, have been designed each resin blend. They are identified in this paper by dates.

RESULTS OF INFILTRACION WITH RESINS.

In table 3 we show the degree of infiltration achieved with different nanoreinforcements, surface treatments, two resin blends one phenolic and one furanic, Fe2 and Fux respectively, different infiltration conditions and the flexural strength and flexural modulus measured on the probes.

Table 3. Probes of impregnated reinforcements, conditions and some results

Reinforcement	Resin blend	Surface	Condition	Porosity % vol	Flexural Strength MPa	Flexural Modulus MPa
1	Fe2	T	211200	3.2		
1	Fe2	T	160101	5.2	90	5.1
2	Fe2	T	211200	3.6	98	3.8
2	Fe2	T	160101	10.7	45	6.1
2	Fe2	T	020201	12.6	38	5.7
2	Fe2	T	050201	7.2	62	5.6
2	Fe2	T	070201	9.5	51	5.8
3	Fe2	T	211200	3.2	107	4.6
3	Fe2	T	160101	10.4	37	2.1
4	Fe2	T	211200	2.8	133	6.7
4	Fe2	T	160101	8.9	90	6.1
1	Fux	T	170101	8.7	59	6.4
1	Fux	TA	200301	2.3	102	10.5
2	Fux	T	170101	10.5	44	5.8
2	Fux	T	060201	4.3		
2	Fux	TA	200301	2.3		
3	Fux	T	170101	8.9	84	6.9
3	Fux	TA	200301	2.2	113	9.9
4	Fux	T	170101	11.4	66	6.2
4	Fux	TA	200301	2.3	111	9.3

From the results found we observe that in general, the flexural strength is inversely related to the amount of voids as we show in fig.6. The non-infiltrated reinforcements have flexural strengths of 5 to 6 MPa.

Fig.6. Flexural strength of probes versus percent porosity

More relevant in our opinion are the flexural modulus figures. We cannot see any clear relation between modulus and degree of compaction, at least for the phenolic blend. In fig. 7 we show the module value of the same probes of fig. 6. The Young module of non-infiltrated reinforcements are 1.0 to 1.5 MPa.

Fig.7. Flexural modulus of probes versus percent porosity

The three high-modulus values belong to furanic resin impregnated reinforcements, with the same temperature/time of reaction profile and same surface modification A. Both parameters could be responsible of the modulus increase.

We had observed in the initial *trial and error* experiments, that the modulus of the infiltrated probes with phenolic resin blends was not much affected by surface treatments. On the contrary, the modulus of infiltrated probes with furanic resin blends was significantly affected by such treatments, this fact can be observed in fig.8.

Fig.8. Flexural modulus of some impregnated probes with several surface treatments.

Special mention deserves the three probes with surface treatment C, because in spite of having a fairly high void content, the modulus is in the upper level. This fact, we think is due to a tight coverage of the walls of the channels and thus a **real reinforcement** of the original porous network.

Fig. 9. Optical image of a furanic-impregnated probe *without* (left) and *with* (right) surface reaction.

In fig 9 (left) we show an image where the void content is 2% in volume, practically located in the reinforcement-resin interface, in this probe no surface modification has been made. In fig 9 (right) we show a surface-treated specimen in which the adhesion in the interface seems to be quite good, the voids are almost exclusively in the bulk of the polymeric matrix.

PYROLISIS

All the previously shown experiments have the objective to cover the original Si O C reinforcement with a carbon layer in order to prepare it for the manufacturing of a CMC.

Pyrolysis of the polymeric material yields carbon matrix. If the polymeric precursor is not well stuck to the channel walls, we will not reach our purpose, and the carbon will be loose in the channels, and no reinforcement of the 3D network will be achieved.

Only a few preliminary pyrolysis experiments have been carried out, but in these we have obtained carbon yields close to expected according to literature. No mechanical measurements of these specimens have been done.

CONCLUSION

1. Three main parameters are of prime interest in the preparation of 3DSiCO/C: a) Precursor resin blend, b) Temperature/time of reaction profiles and c) Surface modification.
2. Curing kinetics of the resin blends are studied by measuring times of gel in a Dynamic Analyser
3. Two blends, one phenolic and the other furanic have been studied. The results applied to optimise the temperature/time of reaction profiles.
4. Several impregnations have been carried out in which the three main parameters have been combined. Resulting probes main characteristics are given.
5. Chemical modification of the nanoreinforcement's surface affects significantly to the impregnation process with furanic blends and little those with phenolic blends.
6. The flexural modulus of 3DSiCO/polymer specimens, is enhanced when the surface of the reinforcement has been modified, in furanic resin impregnated probes.
7. The perspective of obtaining a well-stuck layer of carbon over the surface of the nanoreinforcements is quite near.

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